

AYURVEDIC MANAGEMENT OF ALLERGIC CONJUNCTIVITIS IN 30 YEARS OLD PATIENT: A CASE STUDY

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ABSTRACT

Allergic Conjunctivitis is a common clinical condition faced by practitioners. About 5-22% percent of the world population suffer from some sort of allergic ocular disease. In Ayurveda it can be correlated with Vataja Abhishyanda on the basis of symptoms like Toda (Pricking pain), Sangharsha (foreign body sensation), Achhasruta (watering), Alpa Shopha (mild chemosis), Vishushka Bhava (feeling of dryness), Parushya (dryness), Alpa Dushika (discharge), Kandu (itching) etc. Vata is the chief culprit and other Doshas are associated with it. In these studies, Ksheer Saindhav Pariseka was used as treatment. This treatment modalities showed highly significant results in relieving the signs and symptoms of disease with no adverse reaction.

KEYWORDS: ksheer Saindhava pariseka, Allergic Conjunctivitis, Itching, Vataja Abhishyanda.

INTRODUCTION

Ayurveda is most ancient medical sciences in world. Ayurveda is derived from 2 word that is "Ayu" – means Life and "veda" – means Knowledge. So Ayurveda means Knowledge of life. Ayurveda is not only a treatment procedure, but also a complete life style of a person. In Ayurveda there is 8 specialty branches. So Ayurveda is also called as "Ashtanga Ayurveda". Shalaky Tantra is one of them. Shalaky Tantra deals with urdha jatrugata roga. Netra is also included in urdha jatru, which is also a important organ among panchendriya in our classics.

So it is very important to take care of eyes from different diseases which affect eye. Abhishyanda is root cause of almost all the eye disorder and must be treated as soon as possible, otherwise its complication may lead to severe. Abhishyanda may lead to Vataja Adhimantha, Akshi pakatyaya, Avrana Shukla, Hatadimantha and so on.

Vataja Abhishyanda is characterized by Toda (Pricking Pain), Sangharsha (Foreign body sensation), Acchaashruta (watery discharge), Alpa sophia (Mild

chemosis), Vishuskabhava (feeling of dryness) and so on. The symptom of Vataja Abhishyanda is very similar to the most of the symptom of Simple Allergic Conjunctivitis. Based on the symptom, Vataja Abhishyanda is co-related with simple Allergic conjunctivitis. The prevalence is 5-22% in general population and recurrence found in 41-62% of the cases. So Vataja Abhishyanda is common disease in a day today practice. There is need to find a proper effective treatment in Ayurveda. More over contemporary medicine have lot of side effects associated with it. Hence there is need to find an effective treatment in Ayurveda. In Ksheer Saindhav Pariseka, Ksheer has property of anti-inflammatory activities(Lactoferrin), antimicrobial property(Lactoferrin) bactericidal and bacteriostatic action (Lacto peroxidase), Balya, Chakshushya and Saindhav Lavana has property of stimulating blood circulation, maintain PH balance, Anti-microbial, maintaining normal hydration of corneal Surface for a longer duration, Chakshushya. Action of pariseka is quick and efficient as the absorption of liquid drug through thin layer of eye lid is increased due to heat and continuous exposure of liquid drug to eye lid for a

short period of time. Hence the current study of Ksheer-saindhava pariseka will be taken for effective role in controlling Simple Allergic conjunctivitis.

CASE HISTORY

Patient aged 30 years presenting Pricking sensation, Feeling of Dryness, lacrimation, Itching in bilateral eyes, was brought to the outpatient department. Along with these symptoms irregular appetite and disturbed bowel movements since 15 days as associate symptom was also recorded during history. But there was no history of trauma, surgery, or any systemic health condition in the patient. This was second bout of similar symptoms in a matter of a month. Patient was very disturbed due to the repeat allergic bout. In family history, father has bad history of allergy involving eye, nose and skin got cured by adopting Ayurveda along with yoga. Hence the current study of Ksheer-saindhava pariseka will be taken for effective role in controlling Simple Allergic conjunctivitis.

Chief Complaiints And Associated Symptoms

Pricking sensation, Feeling of Dryness, lacrimation, Itching in bilateral eyes along with these symptoms irregular appetite and disturbed bowel movements since 15 days.

General Examination

Weight – 62kg Height – 170 cm, Pulse rate – 90/min, BP- 110/80 mm of Hg

Personal History:- Bowel – Constipated, Appetite – Irregular, Micturition – regular, Sleep – sound.

Previous History: No history of previous illness.

Family History father has bad history of allergy involving eye, nose and skin.

Investigations

A) **Vision** – 6/6, N6 (OD) and 6/6,N6 (OS)

B) Slit Lamp Examination

Ocular examination	Right eye	Left eye
Lid	PRESENCE OF PAPILLAE	PRESENCE OF PAPILLAE
Conjunctiva	CONGESTION	CONGESTION
Sclera	NORMAL	NORMAL
Cornea	NORMAL	NORMAL
Ant.Chamber	NORMAL	NORMAL
Iris	NORMAL	NORMAL
Lens	NORMAL	NORMAL
Vision	6/6	6/6

Paryaya	Dugdha, paya, Ksheer
RASA	Madhura
GUNA	Guru
VIRYA	Ushna
VIPAKA	Madhura
KARMA	Balya, Chakshushya, Vedana stapana
DOSHAGNATA	Vata hara

Ingredients of Ksheer saindhav pariseka Dravya name- Ksheer (cow’s milk) Dravya name- Saindhav Lavana (Rock Salt)

Latin name	Sodium Chloride
Sanskrit name	Saindhav Lavana
Hindi	Sendhalon
English name	Rock Salt
RASA	Madhura, Lavana
GUNA	Laghu, Snigda
VIRYA	Sheeta
VIPAKA	Madhura
KARMA	Ruchikara
DOSHAGNATA	Tridoshahara

Method Of Preparation Of Ksheer Saindhava Pariseka

Ksheer- Saindhav pariseka (uttara khanda 13/6-7), prepared as per the classical description in Sarngadhara samhita (Madhyama khanda 2/161).

Drugs	Contents	Dose	Method of Administration	Duration
1)Ksheer saindhav pariseka	Ksheer(milk), saindhav lavana	600 matra (6 min)	Medicine is Poured on closed eye lids continuously from 4 anguli height	5 days

Subjective Parameters

The signs and symptoms were assessed by adopting suitable scoring method. The details are as follows:

1. Nistoda (Pricking sensation)
2. Vishuskabhava (Feeling of Dryness)
3. Shishirashruta (lacrimation)
4. Kandu (Itching)

SR.NO	SYMPTOMS	GRADE	
		0-ABSENT	NIL
1)	Nistoda (Pricking sensation):	1-MILD	INCONTINEOUS, ROUTINE WORK IS NOT DISTURBED
		2-MODERATE	CONTINUOUS BUT PATIENT CAN MANAGE ROUTINE WORK WITH DISCOMFORT
		3-SEVERE	CONTINUOUS AND ROUTINE WORK IS HAMPERED
		1-MILD	1-3 IN NRS
		2- ODERATE	4-6 IN NRS
		3-SEVERE	7-10 IN NRS
		2)	Vishuskabhava (Feeling of Dryness)
1-MILD	10-15 MM WETTING		
2- ODERATE	5 TO 10 MM OF WETTING		
3-SEVERE	< 5 MM WETTING		
0-ABSENT	NO WATERING		
3)	Shishirashruta (Watery lacrimation)	1-MILD	2-4 TIMES/DAY
		2- ODERATE	5-10 TIMES/DAY
		3-SEVERE	MORE THAN 10 TIMES
4)	Kandu (Itching)	0-ABSENT	NIL
		1-MILD	INCONTINEOUS, ROUTINE WORK IS NOT DISTURBED
		2-MODERATE	CONTINUOUS BUT PATIENT CAN MANAGE ROUTINE WORK WITH DISCOMFORT
		3-SEVERE	CONTINUOUS AND ROUTINE WORK IS HAMPERED

OBJECTIVE PARAMETERS

1) Slit Lamp bio microscopy to examine Papillae

2) Slit lamp bio microscopy to examine congestion of conjunctiva

Presence of papillae

SR. NO.	Symptom	Grade	
<u>1</u>	Presence of Papillae	0	Nil
		1-micro Papillae	Tiny slightly elevated red dots that give rise to a smooth velvety appearance
		2-macro papillae	Less than 1 mm in diameter
		3-Gaint papillae	More than 1 mm in diameter
<u>2</u>	Congestion conjunctiva of	0-absent	NIL
		1-mild	Congestion in either Palpebral or bulbar Conjunctiva
		2moderate	Congestion in Bulbar and palpebral Conjunctiva less than ½ part of eye
		3-severe	Congestion in Both Palpebral & Bulbar more than ½ part of eye

OBSERVATION AND RESULT

A)

Subjective criteria	Treatment method	0 th day (BT)	5 th day (AT)	7 th DAY (FOLLOW UP)
1. Nistoda (Pricking sensation)	Ksheer saindhav pariseka :	+++	++	+
2. Vishuskabhava (Feeling of Dryness)		+	-	-
3. Shishirashruta		++	-	-

(lacrimation)		+++	+	+
4. Kandu (Itching)				

Objective Criteria	Treatment Method	0 th day (BT)	5 th day (AT)	7 TH DAY (FOLLOW UP)
1) Presence of papillae	Ksheer saindhav pariseka :	+	-	-
2) Raga (Congestion of conjunctiva)		++	-	-

Assessment

1st assessment-1st visit 2nd assessment -2nd visit.

Note- treatment will be completed on 5th day

Clinical Images before Treatment

Clinical Images after Treatment

Need of Paya Saindhava Pariseka In The Management Of Simple Allergic Conjunctivitis

Simple Allergic Conjunctivitis is commonest disease in day today practice. So there is need to find a proper cost effective treatment in Ayurveda.

Seka is defined as,

"सेकस्तु सूक्ष्मधाराभ सर्वस्मिन्नयने भितिः ।" (Sha.S.Ut.13/1-2)

So seka can be used in different types of eye diseases. Seka is usually used to treat diseases which are very strong. PROPERTY OF KSHEER,

स्वादुशीतं मृदुभिन्धवितं लक्ष्मिदिग्मम् ।

गुरु मन्दं प्रसन्नं च गन्धं दशगुणं पयिः। (च.सु. 27/117)

So ksheer has property of Balya, Chakshushya and vata hara

PROPERTY OF SAINDHAV LAVANA,

सैन्धवर् लवणं स्वादु दीपनं पाचनं लघु ।

भिन्धं रुच्यं भिर्म रुच्यं सुक्ष्म नेत्र्यं भिदोषहत । [न.प्रा.]

So lavana has property of chakshushya, vrishya and tridosha hara

Hence Seka with Ksheer Saindhav will be done to find easier and cost effective for Simple Allergic Conjunctivitis.

IN CONJUNCTIVITIS HYPERMIA IS SEEN MAXIMUM AT FORNIX AND MINIMUM AT LIMBUS DUE TO CONGESTION OF CONJUNCTIVAL VESSEL.

HEAT AND CONTINUOUS EXPOSURE OF HIGH CONCENTRATED LIQUID DRUG POUR OVER THINNEST LAYER OF EYE LID (0.05MM)

- a) STIMULATE NERVE ENDINGS
- b) INCREASES PERIPHERAL CIRCULATION
- c) IRRIGATES OBSTRUCTIVE EXUDATIONS
- d) REDUCES INFLAMMATORY LESIONS

CONCLUSION

Cost effective, fast, and safe management of allergic conjunctivitis is noted in this case. As this case shows significant promise large scale clinical studies with all laboratory studies need to be initiated in multiple centers globally.

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